

WEAR PROPERTIES OF NANO-SI-CARBON/CARBON COMPOSITES WITH BACTERIAL CELLULOSE AND BAMBOO CHARCOAL ADDITIVE

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, the fabrication method of Si-C/Carbon/Carbon composites (SiC/C/C composites) with Bacterial Cellulose (BC) and Bamboo Charcoal Powder (BCP) additive and their wear properties were investigated. In order to examine the wear properties of nano-C/C composites and nano-SiC/C/C composites, wear tests were conducted by using the pin-on-drum type tribology tester under room condition and dry sliding condition.

From the experimental results, the coefficient of friction took the low values of 0.14-0.18 during the tests, and the specific factor of wear element loss was $2.25 - 6.77 \times 10^{-10} \text{ mm}^2/\text{N}$. It is revealed that the SiC/C/C composites have excellent wear property in comparison with silicon nitride ceramics and/or DLC coating.

Three dimensional structure of nano-SiC/C/C composites with BCP were observed by using Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) to examine the effect of BCP additive on the wear property. The fibre bridging by carbonized BC fibres was observed in the microcracks over the sliding surface of composites. When the wear element lost by sliding force in tests, the fracture pass was affected by fibre bridging of carbonized BC microfibrils, and large energy was absorbed during crack propagation.

From the results of SEM observations, it can be seen that SiC/C/C composites has relatively high hardness and then, in the sliding on the SUS304 drum surface, the composites attacked the drum surface aggressively. Therefore, the wear powder of SiC/C/C composites consisted of iron materials from the rotating drum made by SUS304. The BC microfibrils, which were combined together with the matrix of polymer, had some effects on the higher fracture toughness of BC composites as increasing carbonizing temperature, and then the specific factor of wear element loss became lower in tests. The SiC additive from BCP could be contributed for low coefficient of friction.

1 INTRODUCTION

Bacterial Cellulose (BC) is a nano-material with unique properties, produced by *Gluconacetobacter xylinus* (formerly *Acetobacter xylinum*), known as "Nata de coco" of diet food. The fibrous structure of BC consists of three-dimensional non-woven network of microfibrils, which is held together with glucan chains and hydrogen bonding[1, 2]. BC fibril is about 100 times thinner than plant cellulose, and Young's modulus of single BC fiber with diameters ranging from 35 to 90nm attains at a value of $78 \pm 17 \text{ GPa}$ [3]. Therefore, BC composite materials could be effectively used as the high performance

structural components for various applications [2, 4, 5]. By using the Direct Impregnation Method (DIM) [6], BC microfibrils network of three dimensional nano-structure and their bonding conditions remains in the BC polymer composites. The BC/Phenol resin FRP plates were carbonized at high temperatures, then we had BC Carbon Fiber/Carbon composites (nano-C/C composites) with new nano structure.

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHOID AND MATERIALS

2.1 BC as a reinforcing fiber

The fibrous structure of BC is characterized by three-dimensional structure consisting of fine network of microfibrils that are randomly oriented and accumulated as in layers. The dimensions of the microfibrils are in range of 2-4nm in thickness, 10-50nm in width and 1-9 μ m in length. *Gluconacetobacter xylinus* synthesizes different structures and densities of cellulose network due to its motion [2]. Therefore the porosity of BC ranges from 90% ~ 94%, and gaps vary within 1 to 20 μ m. Fig. 1 shows the SEM observations of BC sheet. Density of BC sheet used in this study is 0.34g/cm³.

The wide range of nano fibril about 30-500nm, and BC microfibril bundles about 100-200nm were remarkably observed in Fig. 1(a). As seen from Fig. 1(b), BC possesses layered microfibrils structure, therefore BC could be effective in obtaining nano-C/C composite with excellent tribological properties.

Moreover, BC shows mechanical anisotropy, with a high tensile modulus (2.9MPa) along the fiber layer direction, but a low compressive modulus (0.007MPa) perpendicular to the stratified direction [2]. BC possesses an array of unique properties, including high crystallinity, high tensile strength, lightweight, high water absorption, porosity, adjustable aperture and good biocompatibility.

Due to its many unique properties, it has been used in the food industry, the medical field, commercial and industrial products, and other technical areas. By using BC in the fabrication, the composites material offers a prospect of lightweight, fine reinforcement as well as lower manufacturing cost.

(a) Surface observation

(b) Cross section observation

Figure 1: SEM observation of BC sheet.

2.2 Fabrication of the nano-C/C composites and SiC/C/C composites

After getting BC from vinegar maker Ota Suten Company, BC were washed with water repeatedly, and dipped into alcohol. In order to reinforce composite materials with BC, the effective processing method is required for keeping the hydrogen bond between BC and fillers, and physical entanglement of three-dimensionally oriented BC microfibril networks of nano-scale. By using the BC as reinforcement, the water in BC gel badly affects to processing of the composites, especially in the case that the polymer resin is used as a matrix of composites.

In this study, using the DIM method [6], phenol resin impregnates into BC gel and microfibril network porosity gradually, when alcohol is evaporated with water molecules. The schematic

diagram of impregnation process of BC and Phenol resin is shown in Fig. 2. In the first stage, the resol type phenol resin diluted with the same volume of ethyl alcohol as resin, and hydrous BC gel which was immersed into alcohol previously, were mixed. In the case of SiC/C/C composites, Bamboo Charcoal Powder (BCP) additive, which was milled in the size of less than 1 μm to fill and impregnate into gaps of BC microfibrils, was mixed well with BC and Phenol resin.

After impregnating procedure, the BC/Phenol resin mixture with or without BCP was taken out, and dried in the room condition for several days in order to obtain the BC/Phenol resin pre-impregnation (BC/Phenol resin pre-preg) of desired shape.

The fabrication method of nano-C/C composites is summarized in Fig. 3, for SiC/C/C composites as well. The BC/Phenol resin pre-preg was pressed at the pressure of 1MPa at 160°C. In order to obtain the void free composite material, degassing several times for 1~2 minutes, and pressing for 20~30 minutes, then we had transparent BC/Phenol-FRP plate of brown colour (Fig. 4 (a)).

In following, the samples were aged at 160°C for 1 hour, BC/Phenol-FRP plates were carbonized in inactive gas environment (fluid speed of inactive nitrogen gas is 10ml/min), and finally a carbonized BC/Phenol composite material was obtained, that is “nano-C/C composites” or “SiC/C/C composites (Fig. 4 (b)).

Figure 2: Schematic diagram of impregnation process.

Figure 3: Fabrication process of nano- C/C composites.

(a) BC/Phenol-FRP plate (b) nano-C/C composite (c) Testing specimen

Figure 4: Photographs of BC/Phenol-FRP plate, nano-C/C composites and testing specimen.

<i>Carbonizing Temperature</i> [°C]	<i>Heating rate temperature</i> [°C·h ⁻¹]
700	15
500,700, 800, 900, 1000, 1100	10
700	5

Table 1: Carbonizing temperature and heating rate.

Carbonization temperature [°C]	Heating rate [°C·h ⁻¹]	Density [g/cm ³]	Specific factors of wear element loss [mm ² /N]	Mean Friction coeff. [μ]	Wear volume [g]	Bending strength [MPa]	Specific bending strength [kN·m/kg]	Elastic modulus [GPa]	Vickers hardness [HV]	
1100	10	1.42	2.71×10 ⁻¹⁰	0.20	1.6×10 ⁻³	9.89	8.60	10.11	426	
1000	10	1.34	4.9×10 ⁻¹⁰	0.12	1.9×10 ⁻³	8.28	7.40	9.55	355	
900	10	1.23	6.59×10 ⁻¹⁰	0.13	2.0×10 ⁻³	5.88	5.35	8.25	331	
800	10	1.14	8.33×10 ⁻¹⁰	0.18	2.4×10 ⁻³	3.93	4.27	7.21	313	
700	15	1.06	7.74×10 ⁻¹⁰	0.16	11.2×10 ⁻³	3.65	3.20	3.63	218	
	10	1.09	6.27×10 ⁻¹⁰	0.13	1.4×10 ⁻³	6.51	4.13	4.13	213	
	5	1.15	9.65×10 ⁻¹⁰	0.19	0.4×10 ⁻³	4.56	3.72	5.19	217	
500	10	Not measured								

Table 2: Experimental results of nano-C/C composites.

In order to clarify the temperature effect, especially, an effect of carbonizing temperature and heating rate difference on tribological properties, the testing specimens were carbonized at various carbonizing temperatures and heating rates (Table 1).

By the carbonizing process of BC/Phenol resin-FRP plate, BC microfibrils changed into the carbon fibers of nano-scale, and the phenol resin of the matrix became the glassy carbon. The BC fiber volume fractions of the samples ranged from 5.2% to 6.7% while the value obtained for the density of the composites as shown in Table 2.

2.3 Preparing testing specimens

Test specimens were prepared by using diamond saw initially, and basic geometry of 3.5mm×3.5mm×2.0mm was made by using grinding machine (Fig. 4 (c)). A fine scale polishing was undertaken for the wear mechanism, flattening both mating surfaces to improve their load-carrying capability [6]. The sliding surface of specimens was polished with grinding papers with 600 grit and gradually changing to 800 and 1200 grit. At each stage, specimens had 3.0μm, 1.0μm, and 0.3μm of polishing surface roughness, respectively.

3 TRIBOLOGICAL TESTS AND RESULTS OF TWO TYPE OF C/C COMPOSITES

In order to examine the wear and frictional properties of the nano-C/C composites and SiC/C/C composites, the tribology tests were conducted by using the pin-on-drum type tribology tester. The specimen of 3.5mm×3.5mm square was sliding on surface of SUS304 drum of the surface roughness Ra=0.3μm. The sliding conditions were as follows: sliding speed 1.5m/sec, sliding distance 130 km, and contact pressure 1MPa. The tribological and mechanical testing results are also shown in Table 2.

3.1 Specific factors wear element loss and wear volume

In order to determine the wear volume, thickness of the specimen was measured by a micrometer before and after test. The specific factor of wear element loss [mm²/N] is given by Eq. (1).

$$K = W/PL \quad (1)$$

where P is the normal load [N], W is the wear volume [mm³], and L is the sliding distance [mm]. As

seen in Table 2, the mean specific factors of wear element loss varied between $2.71 \times 10^{-10} \sim 8.33 \times 10^{-10} \text{ mm}^2/\text{N}$. The mean specific factors of wear element loss tended to decrease as the carbonizing temperature was increased (Fig. 5). Wear volume loss varied at $0.4 \times 10^{-3} \sim 11.2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ g}$. It was found that high wear volume loss and high wear rate were observed in the case of high heating rate.

Figure 5: Change of wear properties of nano-C/C composites against carbonizing temperature.

3.2 Friction coefficient measurements

The converter was equipped to the wear testing machine, and friction torque could be found from internal coefficient multiplied by a value of converter output.

The friction coefficient μ can be derived by Eq. (2).

$$\mu = T/PR \quad [\text{N/m}] \quad (2)$$

where P is the Normal load [N], and R is Radius of drum [mm] and T is the Value of friction torque.

The mean friction coefficient varied at 0.15~0.20. In this experiment, friction coefficients showed low values and seem to be independent of the carbonizing temperature.

3.3 Test results for SiC/C/C composites

In order to examine the wear and friction properties of the SiC/C/C composites, the tribology tests were conducted by following the same experimental method for nano-C/C composites. The tribological and mechanical testing results were summarized and shown in Table 3 and Fig. 6.

The mean dynamic friction coefficient took the values in the range 0.14 ~ 0.18 during the wear tests, and the specific factors of wear element loss were $2.25 \times 10^{-10} \sim 6.77 \times 10^{-10} \text{ mm}^2/\text{N}$. The wear characteristic of the SiC/C/C composites was related to the carbonizing temperature. The SiC/C/C composites has excellent wear properties in comparison with nano-C/C composites and BCP/Phenol composites. It is considered that the bamboo charcoal powder with carbonized BC fibers played an important role in wear properties, and influenced on wear resistance of the SiC/C/C composites.

Temperature (Heating rate: $10^\circ\text{C} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$)	700°C	800°C	900°C	1000°C
Specific factors of wear element loss $[\text{mm}^2/\text{N}]$	6.52×10^{-10}	6.77×10^{-10}	4.11×10^{-10}	2.25×10^{-10}
Mean friction coefficient	0.16	0.15	0.14	0.18
Density $[\text{g}/\text{cm}^3]$	1.07	1.12	1.21	1.32
Specific bending strength $[\text{kN} \cdot \text{m}/\text{kg}]$	5.23	4.54	14.23	10.37
Vickers hardness [HV]	291	356	356	450

Table 3: Experimental results of SiC/C/C composites.

(a) Specific factor of wear element loss

(b) Coefficient of dynamic friction

Figure 6: Change of wear properties of SiC/C/C composites against carbonizing temperature.

4 SEM AND SURFACE MORPHOLOGY ANALYSIS

4.1 Sliding surface morphology

In order to understand wear and friction mechanism, we examined the sliding surfaces of the composites and contacting drum shown in Figs. 7(a) and 7(b). Moreover, surface roughness tests were performed for morphology of sliding surface shown in Fig. 7 (c).

Figure 7: SEM images and surface morphology of nano-C/C composites and contacting drum.

(a) Worn surface of nano-C/C composites, (b) Contacting surface of SUS304 drum and (c) Surface roughness morphology of nano-C/C composites

The specimen of $700^{\circ}\text{C}/10^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$, the worn surface indicated typical abrasive wear with shallow scratches about $1\sim 2\mu\text{m}$ ($R_z=1.81\mu\text{m}$) produced by scuffing of wear debris powder. As contacting surface shown in Fig. 7(b), a large amount of wear debris was generated, and the adherends to contacting surfaces were observed, as resulting, high wear rate was exhibited. From surface roughness morphology shown in Fig. 7(c), several asperities and pits were observed on the worn surface, and it is considered that the some pits were filled with wear particles.

On the worn surface of $800^{\circ}\text{C}/10^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$, a few wear scars (damages) and microcracks of depth about $1.5\mu\text{m}$ were observed, and the amount of wear debris was smaller than that in the case of $700^{\circ}\text{C}/10^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$. This resulted in displayed smooth surface ($R_a=0.18\mu\text{m}$) and low wear rate.

Viewing the sliding surface of $900^{\circ}\text{C}/10^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$, the pitting and cracking with several micrometers in length occurred in several places, and the surfaces showed the highest roughness $R_a=1.29\mu\text{m}$.

As the carbonizing temperature was increased, the hardness was higher and amount of wear debris became lower. Therefore, these had a possibility of one reason for the low wear rate. Moreover, the growth of microcracks with length of $1.5\sim 6\mu\text{m}$ was observed inside of the composites through sliding, and it led to diminishing of delamination mechanism and showed higher wear resistance.

4.2 SEM observations worn and cross section

We observed worn surfaces of nano-C/C composites at 10000 magnification after tribology tests. Fig. 8 shows the worn surface of $900^{\circ}\text{C}/10^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$. It is seen in this figure that cracks with several micrometers in length were induced on the worn surface, and many BC microfibrils were observed inside the crack. Fig. 9 shows cross section observing of $900^{\circ}\text{C}/10^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$. The photograph of cross section indicates that BC microfibrils of nano-scales were dispersed complicatedly over the cross section, and inter crazes of nano scale were observed.

The cause of the extremely low appearance of crack is due to a contribution of nano scale BC fiber bridging. Fig. 10 shows the fiber bridging model of nano-C/C composites.

A number of studies have focused on the fiber bridging law for composites materials. The fibers bridge the crack surfaces, and then generate stresses such as closing the crack surface during the progress of the crack [7]. From fundamental aspects, if the interaction between a growing crack and the BC microfibrils can absorb a fraction of the energy available at the crack tip stress field, then crack propagation will be affected. In other words, the BC played an important role to reduce crack opening displacement, and as a result, the crack propagation will be blunted.

Figure 8: Sliding surface observation of nano-C/C composites carbonized at $900^{\circ}\text{C}/10\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$.

Figure 9: Cross section observation of nano-C/C composites carbonized at $900^{\circ}\text{C}/10\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$.

Figure 10: Fiber bridging model of nano-C/C composites.

5 WEAR DEBRIS ANALYSIS FOR SiC/C/C COMPOSITES

5.1 Sliding surface analysis

In order to examine wear and friction mechanism, we observed worn surfaces of SiC/C/C composites and the drum surfaces of SUS304 after wear tests. Fig. 11 shows worn surfaces of composites and sliding drum. As shown in Fig. 11(a) for the worn surface of 700°C, a shallow parallel grooves and several deep scratches were observed. Viewing the drum surface of 700°C, a large amount of wear debris adherend like a black film and grooves were formed by the adhesive wear. From the result of observations, the wear mechanism of 700°C was found to be a mixed mode of abrasive- adhesive wear mainly due to adhesion of wear debris, consequently, leading to obtain high wear rate. For the worn surface of 800°C in Fig. 11(b), a lot of wear scratch which were filled with wear debris particles, were observed. The number of wear debris particles on the worn surface of drum, became smaller than that in the case of 700°C. From Fig. 11(b) for the worn surface of 900°C, an abrasive wear track was caused by the hard particles. In the case of drum surface, relatively smaller number of wear debris were observed and the surface damage was observed during sliding. It can be seen that the wear mechanism changed from adhesive condition to abrasive one with increasing carbonizing temperature.

Figure 11: SEM images of worn surfaces of SiC/C/C composites and drum surfaces of SUS304.
(a) 700°C (b) 800°C (c) 900°C

Figure 12: SEM observation and EDS analysis of wear debris of SiC/C/C specimens carbonized at 700°C and 900°C.

(a) SEM images of wear debris, (b) EDS analysis of carbon distribution and
(c) EDS analysis of iron distribution

Fig. 12 shows the SEM observation and EDS analysis of iron and carbon distribution of the wear debris particles of SiC/C/C composites. Wear debris particles of SiC/C/C specimen carbonized at 700°C consisted of roll formed ones, and low intensity of iron was observed. In the case of 900°C, the particles had the shape of flakes, and we observed high intensity of iron images from the SUS304 drum. Considering these results, as increasing carbonizing temperature, composites exhibited a higher hardness, as a result, it tended to cause severe damages in the SUS304 drum surface.

6 MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

6.1 Three point bending testing results

Three point bending test of nano-C/C composites specimen (80mm×20mm×4mm) was performed using Instron 5543 type testing machine. The test conditions were as follows: Cross-head speed 0.2mm/min, span length 48mm, data measurement frequency 10Hz, and indenter radius as 5 mm. The results of bending tests are also shown in Table 2, and the specific bending strength against carbonizing temperature was shown in Fig. 13. Although mean bending strength varied at 3~10MPa, but the specific bending strength displayed high value around 4.4~8.6[kN·m/kg] because of low density of C/C composites.

Figure 13: Relationship between specific bending stress and carbonizing temperature.

As can be seen from Fig. 13, the specific bending strength was increased with increasing carbonizing temperature. By observing fracture surfaces of bending test specimens, it was seen that the roughness on the fractured surfaces decreased monotonically with increasing the carbonizing temperature.

6.2 Hardness test results

The hardness of nano-C/C composites was measured using micro Vickers hardness testing machine. Hardness test results are also shown in Table 2 and Fig. 14. Hardness tests were performed 5 times in each specimens. As increasing carbonizing temperature, the specific factors of wear element loss decreases monotonically. Holm formulated the wear equation in that the volume of the material removed W is directly proportional to the sliding distance, the normal pressure and the wear coefficient, and inversely proportional to the hardness of the surface:

$$W = kPL/H \quad (3)$$

where k is the value of coefficient, P is the contact load[N], L is the sliding distance[mm], H is the hardness[HV]. The agreement between values estimated by Holm's equation (3) and the experimental ones is fairly good as shown in Fig. 14. The possible mechanism for the improvements in the wear resistance, bending strength and hardness with the increase in the carbonization temperature, can be the higher bonding strength between BC fibres and carbon matrices.

Figure 14: Relationship between specific factors of wear element loss and Vickers hardness for nano-C/C composites.

7 CONCLUSIONS

As main conclusions, it was found that:

(1) A fabrication method of nano-C/C composites and SiC/C/C composites, in which BC microfibril network of three dimensional structure and their bonding condition remain, was developed.

(2) The effects of fabrication condition on the friction coefficient and wear properties of nano-C/C composites with SUS304 stainless steel drum were investigated. The specific factors of wear element loss and hardness were related to the carbonizing temperature, in addition to the heating rate temperature. In this experiment, it was found that optimal heating rate temperature was $10^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$.

(3) The experimental results of tribological characteristics were shown for the nano-C/C composites. The average friction coefficient took the values in the range 0.12 ~ 0.20, and the specific factors of wear element loss was $2.77\times 10^{-10} \sim 8.33\times 10^{-10} \text{ mm}^2/\text{N}$.

(4) The SiC/C/C composites had excellent wear properties in comparison with nano-C/C composites and BCP/Phenol composites. The average friction coefficient took the values in the range 0.14 ~ 0.18, and the specific factors of wear element loss was $2.25\times 10^{-10} \sim 6.77\times 10^{-10} \text{ mm}^2/\text{N}$. It is considered that the bamboo charcoal powder with carbonized BC fibers played an important role in wear properties, and influenced on wear resistance of the SiC/C/C composites.

(5) It can be concluded that from the point view of friction, nano-C/C composites and SiC/C/C composites can be used as component materials for sliding parts of mechanical elements; for example, a motor bearing and a mechanical system of humanoid robots or micro mechanical systems.

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